

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING VOCABULARY THROUGH GAMES FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract.

As the globalization increased in the world, the demand to learn foreign languages is raising and one of the most tedious part, pupils face is memorization of new words. In order to solve this problem, games have a strong influence, which makes the process effortles and keeps students awake and energetic. However, it is crucial to find the most suitable one for pupils from 4 to 11. The article concludes and determines the main factors of teaching vocabulary through games, and provide some best options tested in various places over the world.

Keywords: vocabulary games, memorization of new words, globalization, traditional methods, techniques, pronouncation, prefixes and suffixes, upper-intermediate.

For the last decade, learning and mastering foreign languages is popularizing in Uzbekistan, which is creating more opportunities for school children to increase not only knowledge, but also personal perspective to the world by recognizing other nations' culture. Although, they are quite capable to adapt a new language, there are some common borders, they encounter. And the teachers' duty is to find out the best ways to motivate the learners to solve them.

Why vocabulary ?

Young learners need to pay attention to some elements of English language such as pronunciation, spelling, structure, and vocabulary. To master English skills, students must know the vocabulary of the language i.e. a list of words with their meaning because it supports their skills' improvement (Linse, 2005). Memorizing vocabulary is one of the most boring, exhausting and time-consuming task, especially, if the teacher use the old traditional methods and techniques. For example, English is mostly different from Uzbek language according to grammar, vocabulary and pronouncation, which makes harder for students to learn. In addition, researches show that teaching is more productive and entertaining through games, particularly for the young. Whenever the lessons are conducted creatively, the learners stay motivated and focused to gain information given. Besides, they are required to be active participant rather than the passive ones. For instance, matching words and phrases, crosswords demand to ponder and presume the answers to the questions. Games not only include knowledge improvement, but also develop social and communicative skills, as they are generally played in groups helping connect effectively with each other. The students feel connection with their groupmates.

According to a plenty of researches, students, in fact, can memorize and activate the vocabularies rapidly, in case of facing them 7 times after seeing for the first time. However, games are the super powerful tools to fasten this process.

There are several games over the world to teach vocabulary. When they come across a new vocabulary during the lessons, there is, absolutely, a possibility of being familiar to some of the students in the class, as they reach to upper-intermediate level, the words we ask to focus are just monotonous, so to complicate and make concentrative the task, using the word formation has one of the best effect, which we can take as an example. In this game, it is required to build new words using prefixes and suffixes. [Vocabulary Games and Activities for teachers. Peter Watcy -Jones p.125]

It is been reported that students learn about 2,000 to 3,000 passive vocabulary per year. They learn many of these words from direct instructions, but many more from the variety of reading they do. Often, word meaning can be gleaned by focusing on surrounding words and sentences, or context. When using context clues, it is important to remember that the word's definition is limited to this one context. [Nancy L. Witherell. Teaching vocabulary through differentiated instruction with leveled graphic organizers p.34]. The ideas above are from the professor, who wrote the book about educational differences between levels, says another proven way of teaching vocabulary is through

contexts and collecting word families. Another great and popular game used in education is Kahoot, online game-based learning platform which consists of multiple choice quizzes that are available on a website. Second, Crossword puzzles, which are utilized worldwide, are perfect to strengthen word spelling and memory. A guessing game, Hangman, where players try to figure out a word by assuming letters, is mainly for classrooms to introduce vocabulary. And one of the classic, previously well-known play is Scrabble and Banagram played by building word formations with random letter tiles, provide introduction of new vocabularies.

Except these, you can just use pen or pencils if none of them is acceptable for your class, the younger pupils might describe words drawing on paper, or build them, which can develop the picture of the items in their mind.

Conclusion.

Learning vocabulary is considered one of the main concepts of studying foreign languages, which is also, for numerous students, demanding and tedious to accomplish. In case of performing lessons productively, actively and enjoyably with the variety of interesting activities, students can absorb what is taught without any effort. But that does not mean the old conventional methods are inadequate to practice, they actually teach children to be disciplined and tolerant. A number of games exist for educational purposes, which makes the process much faster and easier, and they are the best ways to overcome the problems regarding memorization of new vocabulary.

References:

1. Sahar Ameer Bakhsh: Using games as a tool in teaching vocabulary to young learners(2016);
2. Nancy L. Witherell and Mary C. McMackin: Teaching vocabulary through differentiated instruction with leveled graphic organizers. Scholastic Teaching Resources(2007)
3. Linse, C. (2005). Practical English Language Teaching: Young Learners. New York: McGraw-Hill.
4. Jeremy Harmer: The practice of English language teaching, fourth edition.
5. Pyter Watcyn-Jones: Vocabulary games and activities for teachers.(1993)
6. www.researchget.net
7. www.thefidgetgame.com
8. www.themissdecarbo.com: 15 helpful vocabulary books for teachers
9. www.ebooks.com: Vocabulary activities by Mary Slattery

